

Lusiads of Camoes: Analysing the Maritime Relations of Portuguese and Cochin in the Sixteenth Century

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ABSTRACT

The study entitled, ‘ Lusiads of Camoes: Analysing the Maritime Relations of Portuguese and Cochin in the Sixteenth Century ’ attempts to examine the early trade relations between the Portuguese and Cochin State from 1458 to the 1572 AD. Lusiads or Os Lusiadas was a Portuguese epic poem composed by Luis Vaz de Camoes in 1572 A.D. It is regarded as the most important work of Portuguese language and literature which narrates the discovery of a sea route to India by the Portuguese explorer, Vasco Da Gama. The poem also explains on the Portuguese arrival at Cochin after their rival relation with Zamorins of Calicut which vividly describes the friendly welcoming of Cochin Raja and their trade relations in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. Therefore the study examines the nature early naval trade roots and relationships of Portuguese with Cochin State.

Key Words: Lusiads, Camoes, trade relations, maritime trade

Introduction

The study entitled, ‘ **Lusiads of Camoes: Analysing the Maritime History of Cochin and Portuguese in the Sixteenth Century**’ attempts to examine the early trade relations between the Portuguese and Cochin State from 1458 to the 1572 AD. Lusiads or Os Lusidas was a Portuguese epic poem composed by Luis Vaz de Camoes and regarded as the most important work of Portuguese language and literature which narrates the discovery of a sea route to India by the Portuguese explorer Vasco Da Gama.

Historical Background of Lusiads

Camoes, the author of Lusiads was born in 1524 at Lisbon, the capital of Portugal. In 1554, he started his journey to India and visited the regions where Vasco Da Gama had sailed. In 1554 he reached Goa to meet the Portuguese Governor who was preparing a naval force to help the Cochin Raja in his battle against the rival *Vadakkumkur* Raja –recorded in Portuguese account as Pimento.¹ Therefore Camoes also joined with the navel force and reached Cochin and influenced by the scenic beauty of the land and began to compose the epic. He had collected as much as information from the local people of Cochin and Portuguese officials who witnessed the arrival of Vasco Da Gama. In the middle of a war life Camoes wrote the epic poem Lusiads which gave a detailed narration on the arrival of Portuguese as traders and their naval relationships with Calicut and Cochin.

As the name Lusiads or Os Lusidas indicate Lusitania, the Latin name of Portugal and include the story of Lucitania or Portugal. The poem highlights the glorious deeds of the Portuguese and their victories over the enemies not only over their fellowmen but also over the forces of nature as motivated by the gods of classical mythology. Through the work, Camoes glorifies the courage and enterprise of Portuguese as explorers especially Vasco da Gama and narrates his journey to find out anew trade route to India. The main theme of the poem is the journey of Vasco da Gama’s troupes through the Cape of Good Hope of Africa and their arrival at Kappad of Calicut in 1498 AD. It also includes the historical facts upto John De Castro Duie of 1546 AD. Camoes returned to Portugal in 1570 AD and published Lusidas in 1572 AD.

Lusiads consists of ten Cantos-each with a different number of stanzas- and a total of 1,102 stanzas in Ottava Rima rhyme scheme. Generally the poem has four sections. The first

section includes an introduction or proposition which presents the theme and heroes of the poem. The second is invocation which gave a prayer to Tagidis, the nymphs of the Tagus. The third section include a dedication to King Sebastian of Portugal and a narration include the fourth section which starts in the nineteenth stanza of Canto I where the background story is being told. In the proposition section, the heroes of the epic are Lusiadas the sons of Lusus or Portugal. Camoes speaks on the people of Lusus as people predestined by the fates to accomplish great deeds. The poem include several descriptive passages like descriptions on the palaces of Neptune and the Samorim of Calicute, the locus amoenus of the Island of love(Cantro IX), dinner in the palace of Thetis(Canto x) and Gama's cloths (end of Canto II). A detailed description on the route of Gama's journey and his speech to Melinde, details of sculptures in the places of Neptune and Samorim.

Canto I- begins with a dedication section paying homage to Virgil and Homer and pays a hopeful tribute to the King Sebastian of Portugal. Camoes portrays that the God of Grece watching over the voyage of Vasco da Gama.

Canto II-narrates the survival of Gama's fleet with the help of Venus and landed at Melinde.

Canto III- speaks on Gama's narration on the history of Portugal and its situation in Europe and the legendary story of Lusus and Viriatus.

Canto IV continues with the narration of Gama on the history of Portugal, the reign of Dom Manuel and the crisis of 1383-85 along with his maritime journey to India.

Canto V describes the journey of Armeda from Lisbon to Melinde.

Canto VI describes the Armada's sail from Melinde to Calicut. Gama's troupes had to face with a powerful wind and they pray to Venus who protects them and helped them to reach Calicut safely.

Canto VII- in this canto the poet narrates the arrival of Portuguese fleet on the Indian city of Calicut. "A muslim named Moncaide greets the fleet and tells the explorers about the land they have reached. The Samorim,(Zamorin) the King, hears of the newcomers and summons them. A government official called Catual leads the Portuguese to the King who receives them well. Catual then goes to the Portuguese ships to confirm"²

Canto VIII describes the Catual's visit in the Portuguese ships where he saw a number of paintings that depict several figures and events from the Portuguese history. But a Musim priest in Zamorin's court convinced him that the explorers may cause threat to his kingdom and Gama tries to return his fleet but he was attacked by a group of soldiers.

Canto IX- Gama identifies a conspiracy in Calicut and tried to escape from there. To reward their efforts, Venus prepares an Island for them to rest and helped them to arrive on the Isle of Love.

Canto X- Gama reaches to Cochin and welcomed by the Cochin Raja. Tethys, a lover of Gama predicts the future of Portuguese exploration and conquest. She tells on Duratte Pacheco Pereira's defense of Battle of Cochin, voyage of Magellan and concludes with an advice to King Sebastian.

Lusiadas Narration on Historical Facts

In Lusiadas historical facts are mixed with romantic narration and descriptions. The poem describes on the Battle of Cochin or the Seige of Cochin of 1503 AD. According to historical records, Vasco da Gama was welcomed by the Zamorin of Calicut and gave him the permission to trade within his territory. But the traditional Arab merchants who enjoyed the monopoly of trade in Calicut were not at all happy with Gama and they tried to get rid of the Portuguese traders. They created conspiracies against the Portuguese as they were not traders but enemies of Zamorin. This resulted in an open fight between the Portuguese and Zamorin and Gama's troupes decided to move toward Cochin State.

From the beginning of fourteenth century the Cochin port became prominent. In 1341 AD Cochin State had witnessed a great flood that completely destructed the Kodungallor port and a new island was created known as Vypin. The Cochin Rulers gradually understood the importance of Cochin port and shifted their capital from Kodungallor to Kalvathy of Cochin.³

The Cochin Raja and Zamorins had hostilities each other they claimed themselves as the direct heirs of Cheraman Perumal, the founder of first Chera Kingdom. But Zamorin was more prominent ruler among all the Naduvazhies of Medieval Kerala and they adopted his suzerainty. The Zamorin became more powerful with direct trade with Arab merchants and also got the support from Perumpadappu Kaimal, Edappally Swaroopam , Palluruthi Kaimal

etc. From the beginning of fifteenth century, Zamorin became more powerful and treated the Cochin Raja as Samantha and restricted him in minting his own gold coins and forced to accept the hegemony of Zamorin through customs and rituals. All these accelerated the hostilities between each other. It was under these circumstances the Portuguese troupes entered into the land of Cochin.

Vasco da Gama sent precious gifts to Cochin Raja as 'Tirumulkazcha' which include, a silver plate, a silver pot filled with rose water, precious stones four bottles of perfumes, velvet rolls known as Villes, a large bundle of round pearls and precious stones and specially decorated hats and ornamented knives. Cochin Raja whole heartedly welcomed them and gave permission to buy products like pepper, cardamom and cinnamon from Cochin Later he entered into a treaty with the Portuguese and declared them as the Brother in arms.

Camoës beautifully narrates the hospitality and kind heart of the Cochin Raja in Lusiadas Zamorin understood the alliance between Cochin and Portuguese and decided to attack Cochin. From March to July 1504, a series of confrontations and attacks take place between Zamorin and the Portuguese garrisons at Cochin allied to the Cochin Raja. These were known as the Battle of Cochin or Siege of Cochin. Zamorin was supported by local rulers and Swaroopams especially the Vadakkumkar Raja or Pimento Gradually, the Cochin Raja lost the support from minor Desavazhies and Naduvazhies, and they joined in the side of Zamorin.

Cochin Raja sent his small troupes of 5000 soldiers under the leadership of Marumahan Thampuran Lorenzo – Retino, a Portuguese officer also assisted them and Cameos vividly describes the journey of Cochin army in Lusiads. The huge army of Zamorin could not enter into the territory of Cochin with force and therefore he bribed some army officials and soldiers of Cochin to their side. The Cochin Raja defeated in the war and forced to move to the temple *Sangetham* of Vaipin. Zamorin's army entered in to Cochin and put forward a compromise treaty with Cochin Raja demanding the handover of the Portuguese. But he refused to do so and Zamorin revenged with destroying the Cochin city, and burned streets, public buildings and plundered the Raja's palace.

The brave attitude of Cochin Raja was praised by Manuel de Faria –e- Sousa, a Portuguese historian and poet who wrote commentary on Lusiads in later periods. In June 1504, the Armada of Francisco de Albuquerque arrived at Cochin to help the Cochin Raja and

visited him at Vypin palace. The Portuguese and Cochin Raja again prepared to fight against Zamorin. Palluruthi Kaimal Attulli Panikar and other *Koviladhikarikal* also joined with the alliance of Cochin – Portuguese and defeated Zamorin's huge army of around fifty thousand soldiers.

Camoës compared the Battle of Cochin with the Battle of Marathon of 490 BC. He praised the bravery of Cochin troupes with the Tempophyle in the Battle of Victory of 480 BC. In order to celebrate the victory Cochin Raja gave of permanent grant – of- arms to Portuguese Commander Durate Pacheco Pereira. Cochin declared its freedom from Zamorin's authority and got the power of minting gold coins of the State.

The defeat in Battle of Cochin gave a humiliating defeat to Zamorin and he not only failed to conquer Cochin but also showed his inability to crush the ting opposition that undermined the faith of his vassals and allies. Zamorin lost most of his traditional authority over Cochin and it accelerated the presence of Portuguese in Cochin. The Raja also gave permission to build a place and church in Cochin. However the Portuguese built a palace at Mattanchery and gifted to Cochin Raja and the relationship between Cochin and Portugal improved in later periods. Later, Portuguese officials and merchant sailed to Cochin and settled near the new palace. As a result of this these place known as Fortkochi which became a major hub of European Portuguese culture.

Conclusion

Lusiadas the epic poem of Portugal not only described the opening up of a new trade route to India, but also highlighted the naval relationship between Portuguese and Cochin. With the Battle of Cochin, the Portuguese succeeded in establishing a direct trade route with Cochin and also resulted in the assimilation of two cultures in Fort Cochin, where even now we can see the past remnants of Portuguese influence as beautiful buildings, places, structures, trade and commercial buildings and finally people with Portugal roots. All these are considered as a part and parcel of heritage symbols of Cochin in modern times.

Notes and References

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